

Comparing gait parameters for right-convex scoliosis patients with and without brace

A. Tschirschky^{1*}, T. Jochim¹, A. Heinke¹, A. Żurawski², W. Kiebzak² and H. Malberg¹

¹ Institute of Biomedical Engineering, Dresden University of Technology, 01307 Dresden, Germany

² Institute of Health Science, Collegium Medicum, Jan Kochanowski University, 25-369 Kielce, Poland

* Corresponding author, email: anke.tschirschky@tu-dresden.de

Abstract: The conservative treatment of adolescent idiopathic scoliosis involves often the use of braces. When properly fitted to the individual body and scoliosis shape, these braces can lead to a positive treatment outcome. X-ray-free pedobarography, a non-invasive method to measure the dynamic gait pattern while wearing a brace, offers a safe and effective way to evaluate the brace fitting under dynamic conditions and without ionizing radiation. Gait parameters, measured and calculated from seven right-convex scoliosis subjects, revealed significant deviations ($p < 0.05$) with and without brace. This highlights the braces' impact on the gait parameters like double support and stance phase.

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I. Introduction

The human gait is a complex sequence of movements. A scoliosis brace affects the gait due to the restriction of movement. Children with adolescent idiopathic scoliosis (AIS) are often treated with braces, which have to be individually adapted to the specific shape of the AIS. This process involves a detailed assessment of the patient's spinal curvature, followed by designing and fabricating a brace that provides the necessary support and correction. In practice, X-ray images are recorded standing upright to verify that the brace fits correctly and was adapted to the patient-specific spinal deformity [1]. This objectively validates the static effect of the brace. The dynamic effect in movement and gait is checked subjectively by the orthopedic technician using visual inspection. An objective method has not been established yet.

Previous studies have shown that AIS [2-4] and wearing a brace for treatment [5-7] influence and change the gait pattern. Dynamic analyses of human gait can be used to evaluate the complex process of walking and thus assess the spine as a component of locomotion [2]. The gait parameters of walking speed, cadence, step length, and center of pressure show differences in gait with and without a worn brace [6, 7].

Changes in gait could be used to test the effectiveness of braces and serve as a predictor for the treatment outcome. The measurable gait parameters must change depending on the brace, which must correlate with the success of the therapy. As a first step, this study investigates whether the foot pressure measurement during walking shows changes in gait behavior with and without a brace effect size that could be expected at maximum.

II. Material and methods

This analysis includes seven subjects aged between 13 and 18, with a mean Cobb-angle of 26.7 ° and C, S, and double-

S curvature of the spine. All seven subjects were diagnosed with a typical right convex AIS curvature and treated with a brace. Due to AIS's very individual and non-homogeneous shape, this study focuses on right convex AIS. Table 1 shows the characteristics of the seven subjects.

Table 1: Characteristics of the individual subjects.

gender	age /y	Cobb-angle/°	curvature
f	13	17 thoraco-lumbal	double-S
m	18	26 lumbal, 21 thoracal	C
f	16	20 lumbal	S
f	15	18 thoracal, 11 lumbal	C
m	14	34 lumbal, 15 thoracal	S
f	15	30 thoraco-lumbal, 38 cervico-thoracal	double-S
f	16	34 thoraco-lumbal, 32 thoracal	C

The data was recorded in the Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce or the rehabilitation department of the Pediatric Center in Kielce, Poland, in 2023, depending on the place of treatment. The pedobarographic data were collected using the DIERS 4Dmotion® Lab (DIERS International GmbH, Schlangenbad, Germany). The measurements were conducted by a physiotherapy doctor, a trained user of the device with several years of experience. Before the measurement, the test subjects did not wear their brace for 24 hours. A gait profile was taken over 5 seconds. Each measurement was recorded both with and without a brace.

The pedobarography recordings were used to extract 199 gait parameters with DIERS software DICAM 3. The extracted parameters were analyzed for significance p with the Wilcoxon signed rank test ($p < 0.05$). Further, the difference between the right and left extremities was considered for significant parameters with and without a

brace. In addition, the significant parameters were determined for their effect size (Cohen *d*) and correlation (Spearman ρ) between the gait with and without a brace. Figure 1 shows the methodological procedure in principle. The statistical analysis was carried out with Python 3.12.

Figure 1: Data flow of the study of the brace influence on gait.

III. Results and discussion

Eleven statistically significant features were identified to differentiate the gait patterns from pedobarography between a gait with and without a brace (Table 2). In addition to the parameters of double support, stance and swing phase right, the forces and pressures of specific foot segments show a significant change when wearing a brace. The obtained results deviate from the significant differences for individual parameters described in the literature.

Table 2: Eleven significant parameters ($p < 0.05$) out of 199 gait parameters from DIERS 4Dmotion® Lab calculated from pedobarography measurements with and without a brace with correlation coefficient Spearman ρ and effect size Cohen *d*.

Significant gait parameter for with vs. without brace	ρ	<i>d</i>
Double support	0.9	-0.6
M5(L): Fmax in relation to contact time	0.3	1.8
M5(L): Fmax in relation to segment contact time	0.3	1.7
Stance phase right	0.8	-0.9
Swing phase right	0.8	0.9
M3(L): Fmax in relation to segment contact time	-0.2	-1.3
Rear medial(R): max. force	0.8	-0.7
Rear(R): max. pressure	0.7	-0.7
Toes(L): max. pressure	0.7	0.7
Rear medial(R): max. pressure	0.7	-0.7
M2(L): Fmax in relation to segment contact time	0.6	-0.7

A strong linear correlation ($\rho \geq 0.8$) between gait with and without a brace can be observed for the gait parameters double support, stance and swing phase right and rear medial(R): max. Force. Correlations between the parameters themselves were not considered. Therefore, for example, both the swing and stance phases on the right are included in the significant gait parameters, although these are known as strongly correlated. The effect size of the significant gait parameters differs widely. The brace has the biggest effect ($d \geq 1$) on the gait parameters M5(L): Fmax in relation to contact time and segment contact time, and M3(L): Fmax in relation to segment contact time.

The difference between the right and left extremities with and without a worn brace (Figure 2) highlights a clear extension of the stance phase on the convex side of the scoliosis within a brace. The similarity of the boxplots on the right and left is remarkable. However, only the right stance phase shows significant changes in gait with and without a brace. The occurrence of one-sided significance indicates a dependency on the convexity of the scoliosis. However, it is only possible to draw a data-based conclusion on this through further investigation.

Figure 2: Share of the gait cycle of left and right stance phase with significant differences between gait with and without brace and right and left extremities according to Wilcoxon signed rank test (**: $p < 0.05$, ns: not significant). Sample size $n = 7$.

IV. Conclusions

The results indicate a connection between the gait pattern with and without a brace using gait analysis systems with pedobarography measurement as an alternative to X-rays. For a general statement, more clinical data is needed. Based on the results of this feasibility study, further investigations can evaluate proper patient-specific fitting of braces. After checking the results with more test subjects, the algorithms developed can be used prospectively to assess the gait pattern of a new brace.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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